

The cost of living crisis in Slovakia has a geographical dimension

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Abstract: *The cost-of-living crisis (CoLC) represents a long-standing structural challenge in developed countries that has intensified markedly in recent years, and is increasingly recognized as a global risk. This paper examines the CoLC in EU countries, with an emphasis on Slovakia and its regions (NUTS 3). The study assesses the level and dynamics of CoLC across EU member states and quantifies the impact of income development on changes in the income poverty risk rate (IPRR), with a particular focus on Slovakia and its regions. Using income, price, and poverty indicators at both national and regional levels, the study analyses the relationship between income dynamics and households' ability to cover living costs. The results indicate significant growth in the share of the population unable to cover their cost of living, driven by rapid price growth combined with weak income growth in Slovakia. Slovakia achieved the second worst score in the entire EU for the average annual growth of IPRR. At the regional level, stagnant or low income growth alongside rising prices emerges as the primary driver of worsening living conditions, particularly in economically weaker regions. The findings highlight growing socio-economic vulnerabilities and underline the need for targeted policy responses to mitigate the impacts of the cost-of-living crisis.*

Keywords: *cost-of-living crisis, income poverty, inflation, regional disparity, development*

Introduction

Contemporary society navigates a polycrisis framework, within which the CoLC constitutes a significant component in advanced economies. The CoLC is currently one of the main problems people are facing worldwide, and the Global Risks Report (WEF 2023a) highlights that humanity has entered an era of low economic growth and a CoLC, which is a socio-economic situation or period of high inflation when nominal wages stagnate, while the prices of basic goods such as food, housing and energy grow sharply. As the map of global risks shows (fig. 1), the CoLC, together with the erosion of social cohesion, are the dominant risks in the category of global social risks. The map illustrates the strong links and interconnections between the CoLC and the economic risks that conditioned and caused it, including the collapse of important price system trajectories, trade wars and the bursting of asset bubbles (WEF 2023b).

The CoLC represents a mixed or combined crisis that has a significant impact on households, negatively affects the livelihoods of broad segments of the population and accelerates the “emptying” of financial reserves of middle-income groups of population, as well as causing and/or deepening poverty among low-income households. “Individuals with lower income, those living in deprived areas and single-parent families are disproportionately burdened with the need to alter their living routines by, for example, reducing electricity and petrol usage, buying cheaper (and often unhealthier) foods and cutting “non-essential expenditures” (Younis and Eberhardt 2025). During the CoLC, living standards are depressed to the point that residents cannot afford the standard of living to which they were previously accustomed and, at the same time, they become poorer (Hodgson 2022).

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Fig. 1. Map of global risks, their connections and linkages
 Source: Global Risks Report 2023 (WEF 2023a)

As reported by Global Risk Report 2023 (WEF 2023a), the CoLC is currently a dominant global risk and will remain one for several years to come. The number of households and individuals lacking the financial resources needed to address the accumulating livelihood risks is expected to increase in the next three years at least. This is in line with the findings of the European Parliament’s “Eurobarometer” survey (European Commission 2022a), which highlights that the rising cost of living was the most pressing problem for 93% of Europeans and up to 95% of Slovaks in 2022 (European Commission 2022b). The COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine are generally considered to be the beginning of the CoLC, as these, among other things, caused a significant decline in global economic growth, disruption of global supply chains and high inflation.

Several works have currently examined the various impacts of the pandemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war on various economic indicators and parameters that led to the CoLC. Several research papers have examined the impacts of the pandemic on socio-economic development, inflation and household finances (Adams-Prassl et al. 2020, Almeida et al. 2021, Ball et al. 2022, Benzeval et al. 2020, Bourquin et al. 2020, Brewer and Tasseva 2020, Dorn et al. 2020, Pizzuto et al. 2020, Gardiner and Slaughter 2020, Han et al. 2020, HM Treasury 2020, Lustig and Mariscal 2020, McKibbin and Fernando 2020, Palomino et al. 2020, Bardazzi et al. 2024, Michálek 2024, Militaru et al. 2024). The impacts of the Russian-Ukrainian war, which directly or indirectly influenced the increase in the cost of living, have been analysed, for example, by Artuc et al. (2022), Blot et al. (2022a, 2022b), Caldara et al. (2022), Chen (2022), Eurofi Forum (2022), Kim et al. (2022), Patel (2022), Redeker (2022), Almazán-Gómez et al. (2023), Aunts et al. (2023) and Bruhin et al. (2023), among others. The results

of such research confirm the significant negative impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war and COVID-19 on the financial situation of households.

The risk associated with the rising cost of living has also been increasing in recent years in EU countries, where the share of the population unable to cope with this risk is growing. As wages fail to keep pace with increasing prices, ill-timed tax increases, real welfare benefit squeezes and government support programmes cannot mitigate the income and inflation shocks, so millions of households are facing a CoLC (Mosley and Szendrei 2022). The increase in the population unable to cover the rising cost of living is significantly differentiated, conditioned by multiple factors and determined by countries' economic conditions and possibilities, as well as their fiscal aid policies. As household budget data show, Slovakia is currently among EU countries that are and will be most affected by a CoLC in the near future (e.g. as a result of several measures leading to an increase in prices included in the consolidation package for the recovery of public finances). Persistent political instability, escalating social stratification, deferred resolution of socioeconomic challenges, and inadequate policy interventions have collectively precipitated suboptimal income growth. When compounded by inflationary pressures, these factors establish systemic conditions conducive to CoLC proliferation. The results of empirical research point to two main groups of factors – catalysts of poverty. The first group is factors related to large income inequalities (Ravallion 2001, Kalwij and Verschoor 2007, Fosu 2010, Jędrzejczak and Kubacki 2013, Stankov 2024), the second group is factors related to discontinuity of governance, or associated with failure to address economic vulnerability (Lipton and Ravallion 1993, Krugman 2012, Kearney et al. 2014).

This paper therefore assesses the level and development of the CoLC in Slovakia, compares its position within the EU, quantifies the different levels and development of CoLCs in individual regions and examines the impact of income development on changes in the income poverty risk rate (IPRR). This investigation aims to (1) spatialize Slovakia's CoLC positioning, (2) quantify national temporal trends and interregional disparities, and (3) identify administrative districts experiencing maximal population vulnerability. The resultant data framework supports targeted social policy formulation for affected demographics.

Cost of Living – definition, concept, and methodological approach

The concept of Cost of Living (COL) is defined in economic and social literature as the total financial sum required to cover household expenditures essential for maintaining a specific standard of consumption and social welfare (utility). COL is a dynamic category whose evolution is directly related to both macroeconomic phenomena, primarily inflation, and microeconomic phenomena, particularly income distribution. The concept of the Cost of Living is inherently relative, which is crucial for understanding regional and international disparities. The absolute level of costs necessary to achieve a comparable standard of living varies significantly depending on the geographical location and the economic strength of the region. This global variability indicates that COL should not be evaluated solely in absolute figures but always within the context of the local market and purchasing power. In academic research, it is essential to distinguish between the ideal, theoretical concept of the Cost of Living Index (COLI) and its statistical approximation, the Consumer Price Index (CPI). The theoretical COLI represents an index that would measure the change in income required for a consumer to maintain a constant level of utility (standard of living) despite changes in prices. COLI is based on the premise that consumers are rational and will substitute more expensive goods and services for cheaper alternatives in response to price increases, thereby maximizing their welfare. COLI thus incorporates the substitution effect. The practical CPI is the index used for the statistical monitoring of inflation and changes in the cost of living in a real-world environment. A key methodological criticism of the CPI is that, as an index based on the Laspeyres formula, it ignores the substitution effect. Consequently, the CPI tends to slightly overestimate the true growth in the cost of living, compared to what would be measured by the ideal COLI. The adoption of the CPI as the primary indicator for measuring the growth in the Cost of Living in social policy signals that the key objective of measurement – stability, transparency, and

computational simplicity (via the Laspeyres index) – is prioritized over the theoretical accuracy of COLI. COLI would necessitate continuous and demanding monitoring of changes in preferences, which is impractical for routine statistical surveillance. Furthermore, macroeconomic inflation data, measured for all households, are insufficient for targeted social policy. This is because consumption structures and expenditure weights differ dramatically across income groups. Low-income households allocate a higher proportion of their budget to essential, less price-elastic items (food, housing), which necessitates specialized indices. The Cost of Living exhibits significant differences not only internationally but also at the national level. The primary factors contributing to regional disparities in COL are housing and energy, with housing, including property prices and rents, being one of the strongest regional differentiators.

Beyond the CPI as the primary indicator of Cost of Living growth, several other measures and models exist for quantifying the increase in the Cost of Living, or the "erosion of household financial margins." The foundational concept for this study is the Absolute Financial Margin Model for Households (AFMH), which is based on the financial (in)stability of households. The Absolute Financial Margin Model for Households, as utilized particularly in studies by the World Health Organization (WHO), quantifies a household's financial situation by estimating its absolute wealth in a standardized currency. Traditional analysis of household financial stability often focuses on stock variables, such as total indebtedness or net wealth. However, in the context of the rapidly evolving Cost of Living Crisis (CoLC), characterized by sharp changes in prices and real incomes, the analysis of flow variables is key: net monthly income/expenditure and the inflation rate. Financial vulnerability is primarily a short-term liquidity concept, reflecting a household's ability to cover its financial obligations in a given period (Leika and Marchettini 2017). Financial vulnerability, in the context of household management, is defined as the risk of being unable to cover financial obligations in a timely manner. The quantification of this vulnerability is inherently linked to the household's budget constraint, which depends on income, living costs, and debt payments, as well as the availability of liquid assets. The AFMH quantifies the surplus or deficit remaining for a household after satisfying all its expenditures and obligations. The AFMH can be expressed as follows:

$$FM_{h,t} = Y_{h,t} - LC_{h,t} - DP_{h,t} + LA_{h,t}$$

where $FM_{h,t}$ represents the financial margin of household h at time t , $Y_{h,t}$ is the net income (flow), $LC_{h,t}$ are the total living costs (flow), $DP_{h,t}$ are the debt payments (flow), and $LA_{h,t}$ is the available stock of liquid assets (stock).

The Cost of Living Crisis constitutes a dual shock that directly attacks the individual components of the AFMH. First, there is a sharp increase in $LC_{h,t}$ (living costs, especially essential ones), and second, the real $Y_{h,t}$ is eroded because the growth of nominal wages fails to fully compensate for inflation. For indebted households, rising interest rates further increase $DP_{h,t}$. If FM falls below zero, the household loses liquidity and must either draw on LA , reduce LC (which, for essential expenditures, implies social destitution/poverty), or incur more debt/default. It is crucial to recognize that the CoLC is inherently a distributional crisis due to the phenomenon of inflation inequality. Low-income households, which historically possess a smaller financial margin and limited liquid assets (LA), are the most severely affected. These groups allocate a disproportionately higher share of their budget to rigid basic necessities (housing, food, energy, and healthcare) compared to higher-income families. Since the prices of energy and food rose fastest, the effective inflation rate experienced by low-income households was higher, leading to a steeper decline in their real Y and a quicker depletion of FM . While the entire population faced an inflationary shock (LC), debtors were additionally confronted with rising interest rates, which increased their debt payments (DP). For indebted households, however, the rise in DP has a synergistic negative effect with the erosion of real Y , potentially leading to a higher probability of default. If a household cannot compress its LC or utilize savings, it becomes insolvent. A drop in AFMH below zero has immediate and long-term negative consequences for household welfare.

The Cost of Living Crisis represents a liquidity shock for many households, causing a sharp and unsustainable decline in the absolute financial margin of households. This erosion of AFMH is driven primarily by the disproportionate growth of essential expenditures (LC) relative to net income (Y), which manifests as inflationary inequality. The established and confirmed trend that low-income households spend an increasingly higher proportion of their budget on basic needs (consumption rigidity) limits their ability to respond to an inflationary shock. Reducing these essential expenditures is extremely difficult and leads to numerous negative consequences and social exclusion (destitution). Conversely, the reduction of spending on discretionary items, such as recreation, culture, or dining out, is the first adaptive mechanism, yet it confirms a decline in the quality of life (Béland et al. 2024, Barnard 2023). Wealthier households, in contrast, have the option to absorb shocks more easily by reducing spending on luxury goods or utilizing higher savings. The AFMH model serves as the conceptual starting point for fulfilling the set objectives of this study. For improved international and regional comparison, the parameters of the AFMH model were monitored individually. This means that the erosion/decline of household financial margins during the CoLC was tracked based on the evolution and changes in income and expenditures (i.e., their balance), the rise in income poverty, and the trends in household deposits and loans. The analyses also included monitoring income poverty, which is a condition where households or individuals do not have sufficient income to cover basic living needs such as housing, food, clothing and healthcare. It is a situation where people are at risk of being unable to cover their expenses, often due to low wages or other low-income sources, or high inflation. Income poverty in the context of the model can be understood as a negative financial margin of a household, when household income cannot fully compensate for the costs of basic needs.

The quantitative expression of the monitored indicators and their balance or dependencies explicitly show the state of the population or households in terms of financial burden. Income and expenditure rates are commonly used to measure the level, extent and depth of poverty (Saunders et al. 2002). To determine the performance and position of Slovakia within the EU in terms of income (to assess the cost of living), two indicators were analysed: net annual income expressed in euros and net annual income expressed in percentages. To determine the position of Slovakia within the EU countries, or rather its assessment in terms of the level and development of prices, the harmonized index of consumer prices (HICP) of the Laspeyres type was used (Caisl et al. 2023); this is an economic indicator that measures the change in the prices of consumer goods and services (inflation) over time. These are products and services that significantly contribute to household expenditures and, by their scope, represent the entire sphere of consumption. In the context of the article's focus, it would be more appropriate to monitor only that part of them (basic and essential goods and services) which disproportionately and most heavily affect and burden low-income groups. The main reference period for the index was 2015, which had a value of 100. The analysed poverty indicator used was the IPRR, which expresses the share of the population whose income is below the poverty line expressed as 60% of the median equivalent income after social transfers.

All indicators were monitored as of 2023, as well as their development at the national level over the last decade (2014-2023). The average annual indices were used to compare and benchmark the performance of EU countries. For the sake of clarity when analysing the development of the monitored indicators, ten countries are, at a maximum, shown in the figures (graphs). These always include the three countries with extremely low (lowest) and the three countries with high (highest) values of the monitored indicator and the Visegrad Four (V4) countries. Countries from the V4 group were selected due to their geographical proximity (i.e., they share a border with Slovakia), but also due to the good comparability of many socio-economic parameters, as well as the similarity of their development, whether in the period before 1989 or afterwards. The situation in all EU countries is captured by images (maps), which provide an overview of the average annual values of the monitored indicators and thus the position of individual countries in the EU.

To determine the performance and the position of regions within Slovakia, the net monthly income and expenditure per person, their balance and IPRR were used to examine the dependence between income, IPRR and Spearman’s correlation coefficient. Their development was examined over a period of five years (2019–2023). The monitored period was decreased by half (compared to the analyses focused on the EU) due to significant changes that took place precisely during this dynamic period in Slovakia.

Results

Status and development of income

As can be seen from fig. 2, there are significant differences in income between EU countries. While the highest average annual income in 2023 was in Luxembourg (€49,035), in Bulgaria it was only €9,355. In the same year, the income in Slovakia was €12,744; in addition to Bulgaria, three other countries had lower incomes (Romania, Croatia and Hungary). For comparison, the average annual income for EU-27 countries was €28,217 – that is, more than double the average in Slovakia. The curve for Slovakia shows that although total income grew in absolute terms, the increases were relatively moderate. While net income in 2023 in Slovakia increased by €4,494 compared to 2014, in the Czech Republic it increased by €8,474 – that is, almost twice as much (for the EU-27, the average income increased by €6,700). Fig. 3 captures the development of income in relative values, with the trend line showing slightly better income growth in Slovakia compared to the EU-27 average. The curves also show that the highest income growth occurred in countries that experienced the lowest income growth in the long term (i.e. Romania, Hungary and Poland). Figure 4 captures the average annual income index, which expresses the percentage by which income grew annually in selected EU countries in the monitored period. Nine countries in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) showed an average annual income increase higher than Slovakia’s. The highest average annual income increase was recorded in Romania (9.2%), with a rate almost twice as high as that recorded in Slovakia (4.7%). Of the CEE countries, only Slovenia had a slightly lower income growth (4.1%) than Slovakia. The only EU country that showed zero average annual income growth in the monitored period was Sweden. “Income stagnation” was observed in Sweden during this period; however, given the overall economic situation of its population, this does not represent a particularly significant or extraordinary risk.

Fig. 2. Development of net average income in EU countries (in €), 2014-2023;

Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – *earn_nt_net*)

Fig. 3. Development of net average income in selected EU countries (in %), 2015-2023;
Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – earn_nt_net)

Fig. 4. Annual net income index in EU countries, 2015-2023;
Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – earn_nt_net)

Prices and their development (inflation)

Fig. 5 captures the HICP during the monitored period – or rather, the state and development of inflation in the monitored period in nine countries and in the EU according to the criteria outlined above. The starting point and base year for the analysis of the indices was 2015. The price increase in the monitored period was significantly greater in CEE countries with the exception of Slovenia. While most Western EU countries showed an increase in inflation of up to 25% at most, in the CEE region countries, this rate was at least 10 pp. higher. Within this group, Slovakia was in a relatively good position. From the CEE region, seven countries had a higher price increase than Slovakia by 2023, but also during the entire monitored period. The highest increase in the long term was recorded by Hungary, where prices in the monitored period increased by over 60% compared to the base year. In Slovakia this was 38.8% (the average price increase in the EU-27 was 26.4%, i.e., is lower by 12.4 pp.). As a result, many countries resorted to wage valorisation or tried to increase the income of individuals or households through various other forms of fiscal aid.

Fig. 5. Development of HICP (inflation) in EU countries, 2016-2023;
Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – prc_hicp_aind)

This form of aid in most countries, especially in the CEE region, was insufficient compared to the increase in inflation, and led to a decrease in the purchasing power among a large share of the population. However, changes in purchasing power were also significantly different in other (more developed) EU countries, with the purchasing power of most of the population decreasing. Divergent inflationary trajectories across EU member states are captured through annualized consumer price indices (fig. 6), quantifying real income fluctuations during the observation period. The average annual consumer price index (I_{HICP}) reflects the average annual change in the HICP over the entire period under review (decade). The index I_{HICP} was therefore calculated as the sum of the average annual rates of change (decrease/increase) divided by the number of years in the period under review (10 years). While the average annual I_{HICP} in the west and south EU countries did not exceed 3%, in CEE only Slovenia, Croatia and Bulgaria recorded such values. The remaining countries from the CEE region showed an average

annual growth of over 3%, with Hungary recording the highest at 5.0%. Slovakia, with a growth of 3.37%, was in 20th place, which means that seven countries from the CEE region had higher price growth.

Status and development of poverty

The adverse impacts of high inflation and low-income growth expressed by the net income index (in €) and (in %) were particularly evident among low-income households in Slovakia. This can already be seen in the relatively dynamic growth of the IPRR over the last three years.

The only positive phenomenon captured in fig. 7 is that the poverty rate in Slovakia (14.3%) was below the EU average (16.2%) in 2023. However, while poverty in the EU as a whole decreased by 1.1 pp. (from 17.3% in 2014 to 16.2% in 2023), it increased by 1.7 pp. during the same period in Slovakia. In 2023, Slovakia became the EU country with the third highest income poverty growth. Only Luxembourg (by 2.4%) and France (2.1%) recorded higher growth. According to the average annual growth index of the IPRR (fig. 8), the highest growth was again recorded by Luxembourg, France, and Slovakia, with Slovakia moving ahead of France and achieving the second worst position within the entire EU. The highest decreases in poverty were recorded by Ireland (by 3.99%), Poland (by 3.06%), Belgium (by 2.61%) and Romania (by 2.38%).

Fig. 6. Average annual consumer price index $I_{(HICP)}$ in EU countries, 2016-2023;
Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – *prc_hicp_aind*)

Fig. 7. Development of IPRR in EU countries, 2014-2023;
 Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – ilc_li02)

Fig. 8. Average annual growth/decrease index of IPRR in EU countries, 2014-2023;
 Source: EUROSTAT (2024a – ilc_li02)

Regional level and development of household income and expenditure

Looking at the average annual change in income (fig. 9), six regions experienced income growth, with the highest growth recorded in the Trnava, Trenčín and Banská Bystrica regions. The paradox is that due to high inflation, two regions (Košice and Nitra) recorded zero growth. The very low-income growth in the Bratislava region of 0.3% is surprising; this led to a very rapid income convergence of incomes in the Trnava and partly also the Trenčín regions with income in the Bratislava region during the monitored period. The almost identical trend in income development in the Žilina and Banská Bystrica regions is interesting. The worst values, which were deeply below average (despite favourable development), were recorded in the Prešov region.

Fig. 9. Development of net monthly income per capita in regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

A different perspective is offered by fig. 10, which shows the average annual growth of expenditures, which ranged from 1.08% in the Bratislava region to 10.46% in the Košice region. The low growth of expenditure in the Bratislava region meant that while the regions converged towards the Bratislava region in terms of income, the majority (five regions) showed the opposite trend in terms of expenditure – that is, they witnessed expenditure divergence. Trenčín and Trnava regions showed the largest divergence.

Balance between income and expenditure

The income and expenditure results above indicated several significant facts regarding the cost of living. Figure 11 shows the mutual balance of income and expenditure expressed by the average annual index of their growth/decrease between 2019 and 2023. Negative values were observed in four regions, which means households experienced a financial deficit of (i.e., expenditures exceed incomes). As the data show, households in the Prešov region reported the highest deficit.

Figure 12 highlights the development of the balance between income and expenditure between 2019 and 2023. The graph shows that, until 2020, all regions showed a positive balance between income and expenditure. In 2021, the Trenčín region was the first to record a negative balance. In the following year (2022), the Košice region also recorded a negative balance, and in 2023, another four regions did so, thus confirming a deterioration in the financial situation of the households in the regions.

Fig. 10. Development of net monthly expenditures per capita in regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

Fig. 11. Average annual index of growth/decrease of the balance in regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

The Bratislava region maintained a positive balance, mainly due to long-term above-standard incomes, and the Banská Bystrica region did so as well, due to higher incomes and lower expenses throughout the entire analysed period. A comparison of the graphs of the individual regions (fig. 13) shows that the best position (as indicated by the previous results) was held by the Bratislava region, where the difference between income and expenses per person reached a surplus of €102. The success of the Bratislava region is mainly due to high incomes in the region and, to a lesser extent, is also thanks to the slow growth in expenditures compared to other regions. The Trenčín region achieved a difference that was more than 50% lower (€44) and the lowest overall in the same year (2019) due to significantly higher expenditures compared to other regions.

Fig. 12. Balance of income and expenditure per capita in the regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

Fig. 13. Detailed view of the development of the balance between income and expenditure in the regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

The situation was completely different in the last monitored year, when six regions showed a negative balance. The worst negative balance was recorded in the Košice region (– €71) and the Nitra region (– €51). This was caused by stagnation in income in parallel with high growth in expenditures. While the critical situation occurred approximately at the turn of 2022 and 2023 in the Nitra region, in the Košice region it happened more than a year earlier. The earlier negative balance among households in the Košice region was mainly caused by faster and higher growth in costs. In the eastern Slovak regions and in the Trenčín and Nitra regions, the situation was best in 2019 and worst in 2023, while in the regions of central Slovakia and in the Bratislava and Trnava regions, the best occurred in 2020 and the worst in 2023.

IPRR

The details of the time evolution of poverty in the regions are provided in Figure 14, which shows that the turning/critical year for five Slovak regions was 2021. According to the average annual index, the IPRR increased in six regions.

An interesting and still unexplained fact is the high increase in IPRR in 2022 in the Bratislava region (3.7%) and the maintenance of this high level in 2023. This had an impact on the values of the average annual IPRR growth index, with the Bratislava region achieving its highest values (fig. 15).

Behind these rather surprising results for the Bratislava region lie several factors that need to be identified and the extent of their impact determined. The highest increase in poverty in the region may associate with the income stratification of the population (a part of the population whose income has long hovered around the poverty line and at a certain point fall into poverty). This assumption is confirmed by the results of EU SILC 2022 and 2023, which show that in the Bratislava region, in the mentioned years, there was the highest share of households unable to cope with unexpected expenses in the amount set as the monthly national poverty risk threshold for the previous year. In 2023, the share of such households in the region reached up to 36.7%, while the national average was 29.3% (Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic 2023). The highest increase in poverty in the region could emerge from high living costs, as indicated in the EU SILC survey (2022, 2023). The highest increase in poverty in the region tends to be significantly related to the urban housing crisis. Rising rents can be a major problem, especially for low-income groups, who are unable to pay the rising costs associated with housing.

Fig. 14. Development of IPRR in regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023;
Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

Fig. 15. Average annual growth/decrease index of IPRR in regions, 2019-2023;
 Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

Analysis of the relationship between income development and IPRR in regions

Low income growth in the monitored five-year period significantly influenced and increased the level of IPRR in Slovakia; it also significantly differentiated individual regions. An investigation of the dependence between the height/level of growth in average annual incomes and the height/level of growth/decrease in average annual poverty proved the dependence between incomes and poverty. Correlation analysis (i.e. the value obtained for the Spearman’s correlation coefficient, 0.6289) confirmed a significant correlation between these phenomena; a high correlation was found, and a trend line was inserted through the measured points, which followed a descending straight line. Figure 16 shows that there was a large negative linear dependence between the monitored phenomena (following Cohen’s interpretation of the correlation coefficient).

Fig. 16. Income growth and growth/decrease in poverty in regions of the Slovak Republic, 2019-2023; Source: Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic (2024 – Datacube – Income and Living Conditions – EU SILC), own calculations

At the regional level, it is therefore true that with higher growth in income, poverty decreases. An exception is the Košice region and partly also the Trenčín region, where this large dependence does not apply at all, as evidenced by their more distant position (i.e. as outliers) on the graph. Despite having the lowest growth, or stagnant income, the Košice region experienced a low growth in poverty, and the Trenčín region recorded the opposite trend: relatively high growth in both income and poverty. The correlation is significantly higher if the Košice region is omitted, with a value of 0.8485. According to Cohen's classification, these results suggest a very large negative linear dependence. The graph also shows that the regions with the highest income growth (Trnava and Banská Bystrica) simultaneously recorded a decrease in poverty.

Development of deposits and loans

The results of income and expenditure balance and IPRR, or the calculated values of their indices, indicate that in the four regions mentioned for income/expenditure balance and in six regions for IPRR, many households had to draw on their savings or even take out a loan to cover their expenses. This is also evidenced by the trends for household deposits and loans in the period from 2019 to 2023 (fig. 17). As can be seen, the growth of deposits stopped at the end of 2021, and the amount of household deposits began to decline at the beginning of 2022. This period (at the turn of 2021/2022) is also characterized by a relatively high growth in loans; the amount of loans to households exceeded the number of deposits in the first quarter of 2022 for the first time. The largest gap between deposits and loans was recorded in the third quarter of 2023, when the deficit of deposits to loans reached over 6 billion euros.

Fig. 17. *Development of household deposits and loans, 2019-2023;*
Source: NBS (2024), own elaboration

A clear picture of the development of household deposits and loans for individual quarters of the monitored period (2019–2023) is provided in Figure 18. It confirms that 2021/2022 was the turning point in the development of both monitored phenomena.

Fig. 18. Development of household deposits and loans, 2019-2023;

Source: NBS (2024), own elaboration

Discussion

The findings presented in this study reveal Slovakia's particularly vulnerable position within the European Union's cost-of-living crisis, characterized by a unique combination of stagnant income growth and above-average inflation. The finding that a sharp rise in the cost of living combined with low income growth led to a significant increase in poverty in Slovakia is consistent with the results of Michálek (2025). This positioning demands critical examination through the lens of broader European research and raises fundamental questions about the effectiveness of national economic policies and regional disparities in crisis resilience. The study's identification of Slovakia as the only EU country experiencing simultaneously very low-income growth and high price increases represents a significant methodological contribution to understanding differential crisis impacts across member states. This finding converges with the results of Claeys et al. (2022), who established that in most EU countries, high inflation leads to more adverse outcomes for low-income households, but that the situation varies significantly across Europe.

Each country experienced its own confluence of contributing factors, including divergent consumer patterns, price variations, and national policies. The Joint Research Centre's (2022) comprehensive analysis demonstrates that while inflation has indeed increased poverty unevenly across the EU, the mechanisms driving these disparities are more complex than the simple income-inflation dichotomy presented. The JRC's research indicates that household expenditure structures, particularly the proportion of budget devoted to food and energy, play crucial roles in determining crisis severity – a dimension that could strengthen the present study's analytical framework. The findings regarding the development and trends of the IPRR in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) converge with international research, which underscores the regressive impact of the inflationary shock, particularly within the category of low-income households (Charalampakis et al. 2022, Villani and Vidal Lorda 2022). The authors' focus on the Income Poverty Risk Rate (IPRR) as a primary indicator, while methodologically sound, may inadvertently mask other dimensions of financial stress. Eurostat's broader analysis of poverty and social exclusion (Eurostat 2024c) reveals that 21.4% of the EU population faced poverty or social exclusion risks in 2023, with significant regional variations.

The study's finding that Slovakia achieved the second-worst IPRR growth in the EU gains additional significance when contextualized against this broader European landscape, where richer regions typically outperform national averages (Eurostat 2024d) – a pattern that appears disrupted in Slovakia's case, particularly in Bratislava region's surprising poverty increase. The temporal patterns identified in this study – particularly the critical turning point of 2021-2022 – align remarkably with findings from other European research initiatives. The Council of Europe's (2024) comprehensive review identifies the same period as when Russia's war against Ukraine severely disrupted global markets, sending food and energy prices soaring. This convergence of timelines across multiple studies strengthens the causal arguments presented, yet simultaneously raises questions about Slovakia's apparent inability to implement effective mitigation measures compared to other EU countries. The observed reversal in the IPRR development trend (a marked increase) since 2020 is consistent with the findings of Michálek (2025), who attributes the economic slowdown during the pandemic and, in particular, the subsequent inflationary crisis conditioning the cost of living (CoLC) as the initial/proximate cause for this inflection. The study's regional analysis reveals patterns that both complement and challenge findings from broader European research. While the identification of negative income-expenditure balances in six Slovak regions by 2023 demonstrates concerning trends, comparative research suggests this phenomenon is not unique to Slovakia. However, the speed and severity of deterioration, particularly in the Prešov, Nitra and Košice regions, appears disproportionate when compared to similar regions across Central and Eastern Europe. This disparity suggests that regional economic structures and policy responses in Slovakia may be less resilient than those of neighboring countries. Other CEE countries, especially the Czech Republic, have long maintained the lowest at-risk-of-poverty rate in the EU (Mysíková 2021).

The correlation analysis between income growth and poverty rates, while statistically significant, reveals methodological tensions when compared to broader European research on subjective poverty measures. Želinský et al. (2022) 's work on subjective poverty trends across the EU demonstrates that Eastern European countries, including Slovakia, consistently show higher subjective poverty rates than official income-based measures would suggest. This discrepancy raises questions about whether the present study's focus on income-based indicators fully captures the lived experience of financial distress among Slovak households.

Conclusion

The study's findings carry profound implications for understanding the heterogeneous nature of crisis impacts within the European Union. The identification of Slovakia's unique position – combining low income growth with high inflation – challenges assumptions about convergence processes within the EU economic framework. This positioning suggests that Slovakia may face longer-term structural vulnerabilities that extend beyond the immediate crisis period, potentially affecting its developmental trajectory within the European context. The regional disparities identified within Slovakia mirror broader European patterns while simultaneously revealing country-specific vulnerabilities. The Eurobarometer survey data (European Parliament 2023) indicating that 95% of Slovaks identified cost-of-living as their primary concern – higher than the EU average of 93% – provides external validation for the study's findings while highlighting the severity of Slovakia's position. However, the study's regional analysis suggests that these concerns are not uniformly distributed, with the Bratislava region's unexpected poverty increases presenting a particularly puzzling phenomenon that warrants further investigation. The behavioral indicators revealed through household deposit and loan data provide compelling evidence for the study's core arguments. The crossover point where household loans exceeded deposits in early 2022 represents a critical threshold that aligns with broader European research on household financial stress. However, the magnitude and persis-

tence of this gap in Slovakia appears more severe than comparable European data would suggest, indicating that the crisis has fundamentally altered household financial strategies in ways that may have long-term consequences for economic stability. The study's policy implications extend beyond Slovakia's borders, offering insights into the effectiveness of different crisis response mechanisms across the EU. The apparent failure of Slovakia's income support measures to keep pace with inflation, as evidenced by the deteriorating poverty indicators, provides a cautionary tale for other member states facing similar pressures. The Council of Europe's (2024) emphasis on targeted measures for affected groups and adequate social protection adjustments finds particular resonance in Slovakia's experience, where the absence of such measures appears to have exacerbated crisis impacts.

While the study's methodological approach is robust, the exclusive focus on quantitative indicators may limit understanding of the qualitative dimensions of the crisis. The surprising poverty increases in economically stronger regions like Bratislava suggest that traditional economic indicators may be insufficient for capturing the full scope of crisis impacts. Future research incorporating subjective wellbeing measures and qualitative assessments of household coping strategies could provide more nuanced insights into crisis dynamics. The study's temporal scope, while appropriate for capturing immediate crisis impacts, may be insufficient for understanding longer-term structural changes. The European research landscape increasingly emphasizes the need for longitudinal analyses that can distinguish between cyclical economic pressures and fundamental structural shifts. Slovakia's unique position within the EU's crisis landscape suggests that extended monitoring will be essential for determining whether current trends represent temporary adjustment challenges or indicators of deeper structural vulnerabilities that could affect the country's long-term convergence prospects within the European economic framework.

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